

“CONTROLLED RELEASE LAMIVUDINE TABLETS AS A NOVEL ANTIRETROVIRAL FOR HIV AND HEPATITIS-B TREATMENT: A REVIEW”

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ABSTRACT:

Tablets are the unit solid dosage form which are widely used in the treatment of diseases than other dosage forms as these are convenient and low in cost. Controlled release tablets are the type of tablets in which drug is release in a controlled rate over a specified period. The primary goal of this review is to develop and assess controlled-release lamivudine tablets intended to enhance treatment results for patients with Hepatitis-B (HBV) and HIV (Human Immunodeficiency Virus) infections. Lamivudine, A Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitor (NRTI's), is among the most frequently used antiviral drugs in the treatment of viral diseases due to its significant suppression of viral replication. Lamivudine is the drug which has a short half-life, this has resulted in poor therapeutic compliance due to multiple dosing. The controlled release lamivudine tablets were thus formulated by suitable selection of hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers to create a matrix system to regulate the drug release profile. The tests to evaluate the tablets were based on a very broad range of tests in terms of physical characterization of tablets include, hardness, thickness, friability with in vitro dissolution studies justifying the controlled release of lamivudine, which is important for maintaining therapeutic levels and minimizing peaks and troughs in plasma concentration. HIV is now an epidemic spanning million worldwide. In this context, there is a demand for such antiviral therapies that can be effective, improve quality of life, and decrease morbidity. Similarly, Hepatitis B is a major public health concern in the context of which long-term management may be able to prevent the important complications of the liver. Controlled release lamivudine tablets meet the challenge of improving both adherence and efficacy in treating chronic viral infections. Consequently, the development of controlled release lamivudine tablets appears to be a novel therapeutic strategy for the treatment of HIV and hepatitis B infection, as well as co-infection of the same, which may result in better clinical outcomes and greater adherence to medication dosage. In designing a controlled drug delivery system, the aim is to reduce the frequency of dosing or to increase drug effectiveness by localization at the site of action, lowering the necessary dose. The review highlights the scope of controlled release lamivudine tablets that help in compliance with treatments also improve the quality of life for a patient.

KEYWORDS: NRTIs (Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors), CRDDS (Controlled Release Drug Delivery System), Lamivudine, Matrix systems, HIV, Hepatitis-B, Drug release kinetic modeling.

INTRODUCTION:

The Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP) defines tablets as solid, flat or biconvex dishes that are used as unit dosage forms. They can be made with or without diluents and are made by compressing a drug or combination of pharmaceuticals. Depending on the amount of medication and the desired method of administration, tablets can vary significantly in size, weight, and form. [1]

➤ Tablet Preparation Methods [2]:

Tablets are prepared by three methods: Wet granulation, Dry granulation, and Direct compression method.

A] Wet Granulation Method: Wet granulation is one of the methods of tablet manufacturing where active ingredients and excipients are blended with a liquid binder to form granules, which are then dried, sized, and compressed into tablets. This improves the flow, compaction, and uniformity of the powder blend.

B] Dry granulation method: The technique of dry granulation, which is perfect for materials that are sensitive to moisture, involves compacting powdered substances into granules or slugs without the use of liquid, then milling and compressing the mixture into tablets.

C] Direct compression method: Direct compression is a manufacturing process that minimizes the need for granulation by compressing the pharmaceutical component, usually referred to as the API and excipients, into the tablets directly. This process can be very cost-effective and quick, especially when working with materials that compress and flow effectively.

Classification of Tablets ^[3,4]:

Category	Subcategory	Description
A] Based on composition	Film-coated tablets	Containing a layer of protection, taste masked, or prolonged release layer coating to protect it, such as sugar-coated, or film-coated.
	Enteric-coated tablets	Intended to resist dissolution in the stomach so that release is permitted in the intestines.
	Controlled release tablets	Release the active ingredient for a longer duration.
	Sustained release tablets	Maintain therapeutic level for longer times without dosing regularly.
	Effervescent tablets	Containing effervescent agents, which may dissolve in water to give a solution liberating carbon dioxide
	Plain tablets	Composed of the active ingredient and excipients but no special coatings or alterations.
B] Based on Manufacturing	Direct compression	Made by compressing the powdered blend directly without granulation.
	Granulated tablets	Prepared by granulation of the powder mix before compression, improving flow and compressibility.
C] Based on Release Mechanism	Immediate release tablets	Release the active ingredient quickly after administration.
	Delayed release tablets	Release the active ingredient after a specified delay, often because of enteric coating.

	Extended-release tablets	Designed to administer the active ingredient gradually over a longer period.
D] Tablets used in the Oral Cavity	Lozenges and Troches	These are solid dosage forms that slowly dissolve in the mouth to be released locally.
	Sublingual tablets	Tablets that are positioned beneath the tongue to quickly pass through the mucous membrane.
	Dental tablets	Designed for dental purposes like, mouth ulcers or oral hygiene preparations.
	Buccal tablets	Tablets are placed between the cheek and the gum for absorption by the buccal mucosa.
	Dental cones	Cone shaped and more localized actions in the oral cavity.
	Mouth dissolving tablets	Dissolving in the oral cavity rapidly and without the need for irrigation.
E] Oral tablets for ingestion	Standard Compressed Tablets	These consist of regular compressed tablets that do not contain any special coatings or release mechanisms.
	Multiple Compressed Tablets:	These tablets consist of one or more layers compressed in conjunction with one another, including compression-coated tablets.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Compression Coated Tablets: a) Sugar coated b) Film coated tablets c) Gelatin coated tablets d) Enteric coated tablets 	Tablets that have a small layer of coating material applied to them in order to shield the medication, hide its flavor, or regulate the release of an active ingredient are known as coated tablets. It may be enteric, film-based, or sugar-based.

	➤ Layered tablet	Layered tablets are composed of two or more layers that differ from one another. Each of these layers contains different active ingredients or excipients.
	➤ Inlay tablet	Inlay tablets have a core of one active ingredient which is covered by a layer containing another. Such a design allows for the controlled release of different components, and most often it is done providing a combination therapy.
	Targeted Tablets: a) Floating Tablet b) Colon Targeting Table	Targeted tablets are oral dosage forms specifically designed to deliver the API locally, where the effect of the drug is required so that therapeutic efficacy with minimal side effects is attained.
	Chewable tablets	Tablets that can be chewed. Primarily use for childrens.
	Dispersible tablets	Tablets that disperse quickly in water, forming a solution that can be consumed easily.
F] Tablets Administered by various Routes	Vaginal tablets	Tablets meant for vaginal cavity administration; they are usually for local or systemic therapy..
	Rectal tablets	Tablets to be introduced in the rectum for local or systemic action.
	Implants	These implanted within the body like subdermal implants.
G] Tablets used to prepare solution	Effervescent tablets	Tablets which release CO_2 in solution when dissolved in it.

	Molded tablets	These are moulded tablets which are supposed to dissolve fast in water so that a solution is formed by them.
	Tablet Triturate	Tablets that are triturate powder so dissolved in water or given in diluted doses.

Table no. 1: Classification of Tablets

Controlled Release (CR) Tablets ^[5,6,7]: Controlled drug delivery refers to the delivery of drug at a predetermined rate at a location that is determined by the body's needs or the disease state, over time. Ideally, two major objectives exist for these systems. These are spatial delivery, which is in relation to controlling where the drug should be released, and the temporal drug delivery, wherein the drug is delivered over an extended period of time during treatment.

Pros of CRDDS:

- Avoid patient compliance problems.
- Employ less total drug.
- Minimize systemic side effects.
- Obtain less potentiation or reduction in drug activity with chronic use.
- Minimize drug accumulation with chronic dosing.
- Improve efficiency in treatment
- Economy

Cons of CRDDS:

- Inconvenient
- Impossible to monitor
- It should be calculated so that over administration is avoided
- High dose of the drug may be lost to those parts that are not reaching the targeted organ
- Expensive
- Dose dumping i.e, large amount of drug in formulation is release rapidly and leads to toxicity.

Disease Profile:

- **HIV**: HIV is an abbreviation for the term Human Immunodeficiency Virus. AIDS is an abbreviation of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome. In HIV, H-It infects only humans and transmitted between humans not from animals. I-The human body has a system called immune system whose main function is to protect our body from germs, infections etc. But a person suffering from HIV has inability to fight against diseases. However, immune system becomes deficient. V-Virus is a small, simplest thing which is in inactive form outside the body and becomes active when it goes inside human body. (70) HIV is a virus that causes AIDS. Normally, our body has immune system that attack viruses and bacteria. Immune system has white blood cells which protect us from infections. White blood cells contain CD4+ cells which is also known as helper cells or T cells. A person that

is infected will be in a position to develop. These infections rely on body's immune system. These infections result in some health issues and can lead to the death of an individual. [8]

Stages of HIV: There are 3 stages of HIV and increase in severity as increase in the stage.

Approximately 90% of patients with acute HIV experience at least 1 symptom within the first 4 weeks after primary HIV infection: Fever, Fatigue, Muscle pain, Skin rash, Headache, Sore throat, Swollen lymph nodes, Joint pain, Night sweats, Diarrhoea. The onset of symptoms is acute and generally occurs at 2 to 4 weeks postinfection. The duration of symptoms averages 18 days, and resolution of symptoms coincides with the establishment of a viral replication set point approximately 30 days postinfection. Without therapy, higher viral load and worse severity and longer duration of conversion illness are early predictors of poor prognosis. Mucocutaneous ulceration is a characteristic feature of acute HIV, which is characterized by shallow, sharply demarcated ulcers that have a white base surrounded by a thin area of erythema. Acute aseptic meningoencephalitis is described as a clinical syndrome of acute HIV

Fig.no.1: Structure of the HIV virus

Chronic HIV: After HIV infection and formation of the viral set point, patients enter the chronic phase of the infection. In general, most patients with chronic HIV are asymptomatic until the onset of AIDS. Nevertheless, nonspecific fatigue may be present, and persistent generalized lymphadenopathy is common. Generalized lymphadenopathy is defined as 3 to 6 months of

enlarged lymph nodes at more than 2 non-contiguous sites that are not inguinal and not accounted for by another lymphoproliferative or infectious cause. The chronic HIV patient can develop oropharyngeal candidiasis, cervical dysplasia or carcinoma in situ, recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis, oral hairy leucoplakia, and disseminated cutaneous herpes simplex virus. Skin manifestations like molluscum contagiosum infections, bacillary angiomatosis, seborrheic dermatitis, varicella-zoster virus reactivations are common and severe in HIV patients.^[9]

AIDS The third stage is simply called Acquired Immuno deficiency Syndrome and is the most severe stage of HIV infection. In this stage, the HIV has severely ravaged the immune system and the body is unable to fight the opportunistic infections. Individuals infected by HIV are considered to have AIDS if their CD4 count is below 200 cells/mm. A person diagnosed with AIDS has a very high viral load that makes the transmission of disease to other people very easy. In the absence of treatment, a person with AIDS survives for up to 3 years. ^[9]

Hepatitis B:

Hepatitis B is a virus infections remains one of the world's most common infections due to acute and chronic hepatitis, severe liver damage, and death. The primary modes of transmission include infected mothers passing it on to their children and through infected blood and body fluids. Screening is therefore encouraged for pregnant women, adolescents, and adults at high risk. The initial diagnosis is based on serological tests for acute and chronic hepatitis, which then pave the way for molecular assays, including detection and quantification of viral DNA, genotyping determination, and mutation analysis. All patients diagnosed with chronic hepatitis B should be given antiviral drugs, with frequent monitoring; however, effective therapies for treating hepatitis B include nucleoside analogs as well as pegylated interferons, which decrease the rate of liver cancer, prevent liver transplants, and sometimes stop or reverse the progression of the disease in the liver. Initial evaluation of HBV infection by meticulous patient history, physical examination, and assessments of the activity of liver disease, coupled with interpretations of hepatitis markers, include the identification of several key markers: HBsAg, HBcAg, HBeAg, anti-HBs, anti-HBc, anti-HBc IgM, and anti-HBe. The Hepatitis B diagnosis done by using the triple serological marker panel: HBsAg, anti-HBs, and total anti-HBc. To define the stages of HBV infection, the following tests are performed: HBsAg, HBeAg/anti-HBe, HBV DNA assays, liver function tests (AST and ALT), and either transient elastography (Fibroscan) as a non-invasive alternative or a needle liver biopsy to evaluate cirrhosis ^[10]

Prevalence of Hepatitis B Co-Infection among HIV Positive Patients:

The hepatitis B virus, or HBV, is a serious global health burden, with the primary cause of liver disease. It is estimated that about 360 million people worldwide are affected with chronic forms of the virus. It leads to severe complications like cirrhosis and liver cancer in more immunocompromised patients, mainly those infected with HIV. This mainly attacks CD4 positive T cells, which play a central role in immune response. When HIV destroys these cells, it compromises cellular and humoral immunity, thus leaving the patients prone to secondary infections, of which HBV is one. Several HIV patients have been found co-infected with HBV; hence, prevalence of hepatitis B among this patient population is critical for planning appropriate treatment. It is therefore a review article that has focused on summarizing the recently published

literature pertaining to the prevalence of hepatitis B co-infection among individuals infected with HIV across the world^[11]

	HIV	Hepatitis-B
Affected body part	Immune system	Liver
Type of virus	Retrovirus which targets and attack immune system particularly CD4 T-cells (Helper T cells)	DNA virus that affects liver and cause both acute and chronic liver disease
Transmission mode	Through contact with infected bodily fluids including (blood, semes, vaginal fluids, breast milk)	Through the contact with infected bodily fluids, but it is more reilient outside body
Symptoms	Flu like symptoms, fever, sore throat, fatigue, as disease progress it leads to AIDS	Fatigue, jaundice, abdominal pain, dark urine, nausea
Treatment	ART (antiretroviral therapy) there is no cure for HIV but it can Manage as chronic condition	ART (antiretroviral therapy) Reduce viral load and prevent liver damage
ART used	Lamivudine,Rilpivirine, Doravirine	Lamivudine, Tenofovir alafenamide, Entecavir

Table no. 2: HIV And Hepatitis B

➤ **HIV Treatment ARTs**^[12]:

Type of drug	Examples
Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors (NRTIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF) • Emtricitabine (FTC) • Lamivudine (3TC)
Non-Nucleoside Reverse Transcriptase Inhibitors (NNRTIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efavirenz (EFV) • Rilpivirine (RPV) • Doravirine (DOR)
Protease Inhibitors (PIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atazanavir (ATV) • Darunavir (DRV) • Lopinavir (LPV) with Ritonavir (RTV)
Integrase Strand Transfer Inhibitors (INSTIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raltegravir (RAL) • Elvitegravir (EVG) • Dolutegravir (DTG)

Entry Inhibitors:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maraviroc (MVC) (CCR5 antagonist) • Enfuvirtide (T20) (fusion inhibitor)
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Table no. 3: HIV Treatment ARTs

➤ **Hepatitis B Treatment Antivirals** ^[10]

Type of drug	Example
Nucleoside Analogues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lamivudine (3TC) • Tenofovir alafenamide (TAF) • Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF) • Entecavir (ETV) • Adefovir dipivoxil (ADV)
Pegylated Interferons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peginterferon alfa-2a: Used for chronic hepatitis B, it helps boost the immune response against HBV.

Table no. 4: Hepatitis B Treatment Antivirals

DRUG PROFILE ^[13]

➤ **Lamivudine:**

- **Lamivudine**, also called 3TC, it is an Antiretroviral medication used to prevent and treat HIV. It is also used to treat chronic Hepatitis B when other options are not possible.
- **Formula Weight:** 229.3
- **Merck Index:** 5367
- **Product Group:** Antiviral
- **BCS Class:** BCS III (High solubility Low permeability)
- **Log p:** 1.2
- **Pka:** 5.5
- **PH:** 4 - 5.5 (slightly acidic)
- **Wavelength:** 270 nm
- **Beer's Lamberts range:** 4-20 µg/ml

- **CAS number:** 134678-17-4
- **IUPAC Name:** 4-amino-1-[(2R,5S)-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-yl]-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-2-one
- **Type:** Small Molecule
- **Groups:** Approved, Investigational
- **Weight:** Average: 229.256
Monoisotopic: 229.052111923
- **Chemical Formula:** C₈H₁₁N₃O₃S
- **Pharmacodynamics:** Lamivudine is a member of the class of NRTIs. It is an antiviral drug with actions against HIV-1 and HBV because it blocks viral DNA synthesis. When activated through phosphorylation, the parent drug has active metabolites that are competitive substrates for incorporation into viral DNA. Once incorporated into DNA, the metabolites of lamivudine competitively inhibit the action of HIV reverse transcriptase and serve as a chain terminator of DNA synthesis. Because they lack the 3'-OH group, incorporated nucleoside analogues cannot form the essential 5' to 3' phosphodiester linkage in the elongation step of DNA chain synthesis.
- **Mechanism of action:** Lamivudine is a synthetic nucleoside analogue, phosphorylated intracellularly to its active 5'-triphosphate metabolite, known as lamivudine triphosphate (L-TP). It acts by incorporation into the viral DNA through the action of the reverse transcriptase of HIV and HBV polymerase, which leads to chain termination.
- **Absorption:** Lamivudine was rapidly absorbed after oral administration in HIV-infected patients. Absolute bioavailability is 86% for the 150-mg tablet and 87% for the oral solution. The peak serum lamivudine concentration (C_{max}) is 1.5 ± 0.5 mcg/mL when an oral dose of 2 mg/kg twice a day was given to HIV-1 patients.
- **Volume of distribution:** Apparent volume of distribution, IV administration = 1.3 ± 0.4 L/kg.
- **Protein binding:** <36% bound to plasma protein.
- **Metabolism:** The only known metabolite of lamivudine is the trans-sulfoxide metabolite. This biotransformation is catalyzed by sulfotransferases.
- **Excretion:** Most of the lamivudine is excreted unchanged in the urine by active organic cationic secretion. 5.2% ± 1.4% (mean ± SD) of the dose was excreted as the trans-sulfoxide metabolite in the urine.
- **Half-life:** 5 to 7 hours
- **Clearance:**
Renal clearance: 199.7 ± 56.9 mL/min [300 mg oral dose, healthy subjects]
Renal clearance: 280.4 ± 75.2 mL/min [single IV dose, HIV-1-infected patients]
Total clearance: 398.5 ± 69.1 mL/min [HIV-1-infected patients]
- **International/Other Brands:**
Amilitrap(Dosa) / Antiheb(Mebiphar) / Avilam(Beximco) / Avolam(RanbaxyLaboratories) / EpivirHBV(GlaxoSmithKline) / Flamivud(Flamingo Pharmaceuticals) / Ganvirel(Ivax) / Hepavir(Square) / Hepitec(GlaxoSmithKline) / Lamda(Cadila) / Lamibergen(Paylos) / Lamidac(Zydus) / Lamitec(ZifamIndia) / Lamivir(Incepta) / Zeffix (GlaxoSmithKline)

Lamivudine, used in combination with other drugs for the treatment of HIV-1 and as a monotherapy in the cases of hepatitis B virus. It reduces viral load effectively, improves CD4+

counts, improves patients' quality of life. It is considered a virustatic agent rather than virucidal. The drug was approved for HIV-1 treatment in 1995 and for HBV in 1998. Lamivudine is well characterized as being highly effective in combination therapies, that prevent drug resistance in HIV-1 patients, particularly against the M184V mutation. Lamivudine is among drugs listed by the World Health Organization in the "List of Essential Medicines," which reflects the drug's significant importance globally in treatments for viral infections.^[14] Lamivudine 150 mg and 300 mg tablets, oral solution (10 mg/mL) are available for treatment of HIV. Standard dose is 300 mg daily, can be dosed 150 mg twice-daily or 300 mg once-daily with or without food.^[15]

Marketed dosage forms of Lamivudine along with their Brand names, Active ingredients, Strength:

Dosage form	Brand Name	Active Ingredient	Strength	Indication
A] Tablets	1] Epivir	Lamivudine	150 mg, 300 mg	HIV treatment
	2] Zeffix	Lamivudine	100 mg	Chronic Hepatitis B treatment
	3] Combivir	Lamivudine, Zidovudine	Lamivudine 150mg, Zidovudine 300mg	HIV treatment (Combination therapy)
	4] Triumeq	Lamivudine, Dolutegravir, Abacavir	Lamivudine 300mg, Dolutegravir 50mg, Abacavir 600mg	HIV treatment (Combination therapy)
B] Combination Tablets	1] Epzicom	Lamivudine, Abacavir	Lamivudine 300mg, Abacavir 600mg	HIV treatment (Combination therapy)
	2] Trizivir	Lamivudine, Abacavir, Zidovudine	Lamivudine 150mg, Abacavir 300mg, Zidovudine 300mg	HIV treatment (Combination therapy)
C] Oral Solutions	1] Epivir Oral solution	Lamivudine	10 mg/mL	Pediatric HIV treatment

	2] Zeffix Oral Solution	Lamivudine	5 mg/mL	Chronic Hepatitis B treatment
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Table no. 5: Marketed dosage forms of Lamivudine along with their Brand names, Active ingredients, Strength

MATERIALS AND METHOD: Lamivudine (API), Eudragit RS 100, HPMC K 100M, PVP K 30, Aerosil, Lactose, Talc, Magnesium stearate.

Active agent	Use	Range in %(w/w) of total tablet weight
Lamivudine	API	300 mg
Eudragit RS 100	Matrix forming agent	15-35 %
HPMC K 200 M	Polymer	5-20%
PVP K 30	Binder	2 -10 %
Aerosil	Glidant	0.1-1
Lactose	Filler	10- 80%
Talc	Anti-adherent	1-5 %
Magnesium stearate	Lubricant	0.25-2

Table no. 6: Active ingredients and Excipients used in the preparation of Lamivudine Controlled release tablet

Preformulation studies: Preformulation studies are the preformulation investigations carried out on a drug substance before formulating it into a dosage form, such as tablets or capsules. These studies make it possible for us to understand physical and also chemical properties of drugs.

➤ Evaluation of granules:

1) Angle of Repose: Angle of repose (θ) Used in assessing flowability of granules The angle of repose is assessed by fixed funnel method whereby free flowing granules are allowed to fall from a funnel and pile up on a horizontal surface and then a conical heap is formed.

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{h}{r}$$

Where, h = height of the cone And r = radius of the base of cone.

The smaller angle will provide better flow characteristics. Conversely, the higher angle will signify a condition of poor flowing.

Sr. No.	Flowability	Angle Of Repose
1	Excellent	<25
2	Good	25-30
3	Moderate Flow	30-40

Table no. 7: Relationship between Angle of Repose and Flowability

2) **Bulk Density:**

4	Poor Flow	>40
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 Bulk density is defined as mass of granules per bulk volume, i.e. volume occupied by granules without tapping. It can be calculated through the following relation

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \text{Weight of powder} / \text{Bulk volume}$$

3) **Tapped Density:** Tapped density is obtained by measuring the volume of granules after passing them through a number of mechanical taps. About 100 times tapping is done. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Tapped Density} = \text{Weight of powder} / \text{Tapped volume}$$

Tapped density is also given in g/cc. A high difference between bulk and tapped density may indicate poor flowability and potential problems at compression.

4) **Bulkiness:** Bulkiness is the inverse of bulk density and gives the volume taken up by 1 g of the granules. Its units are in cc/g.

$$\text{Bulkiness} = 1 / \text{Bulk density}$$

5) **Compressibility Index:** Compressibility Index is an empirical method of measuring the flowability of granules based on the difference between tapped density and bulk density.

$$\text{Carr's Index} = \frac{\text{Tapped Density} - \text{Bulk Density}}{\text{Tapped Density}} \times 100$$

A high compressibility index often signifies poor flowability while a lower value indicates better flow properties.

6) **Hausner's Ratio:** The Hausner's ratio is another way of assessing the flowability of granules and is expressed as,

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

Sr. No.	Flowability	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
1	Excellent	0-10	1.00-1.11
2	Good	10-15	1.12-1.18
3	Fair	16-20	1.19-1.25
4	Possible	21-25	1.26-1.34
5	Poor	26-31	1.35-1.34

Table no. 8: Relationship between Carr's Index, Hausner's Ratio and Flowability

➤ **Pre-compression evaluation parameters:**

1) **Determination of Melting Point:** Melting point of determined by the capillary method. Powdered small quantity of a drug is taken and inserted inside a very thin glass tube with a tight seal at one end. That tube is connected to a thermometer and apparatus is heated. Once the drug begins to melt, the temperature at which it melts is recorded.

2) **Solubility:** Solubility studies determine how the drugs dissolve in various media, especially gastric (pH 1.2) and intestinal fluids (pH 6.8). An excess of the drug is added to model solutions

simulating gastric and intestinal fluids and it is agitated for 24 hours. The suspensions are filtered, and the degree of dissolution is determined by a spectrophotometer.

3) Compatibility Studies: This ensure that the drug combines well with other excipients in the formulation. The drug and the excipients are analyzed by DSC, FTIR where potential interactions about the performance of the drug are detected.

4) Identification of Drug: This is carried out to determine the nature of the drug. A bit amount of the drug is dissolved in CO₂-free water and titrated with sodium hydroxide that has a colour-indicating dye. The result helps to determine the amount of drug present.

➤ **Evaluation of Controlled Release (CR) tablets:** ^[16] Post-Compression evaluation are as follows:

1) Hardness Test: The hardness of a tablet is checked by a Monsanto hardness tester and also by Pfizer hardness tester where pressure is applied to ascertain how much force the tablet could withstand before breaking. It expressed in kg/cm².

2) Friability Test: Friability is the gain or loss in weight that occurs during handling or in transportation. A Roche Friabilator rotates 20 tablets for 4 minutes i.e, 100 RPM (Revolutions Per Minutes). A weight loss of more than 1% should be considered unacceptable.

$$\text{Friability (\%)} = \frac{\text{Initial Weight} - \text{Final Weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100$$

3) Content Uniformity Test: The test ensures the uniform drug release within each tablet. 20 tablets are randomly selected and analyzed for the drug content in each of them. This batch is said to have cleared the content uniformity test if the drug content in all the tablets falls between 85% to 115% of the drug labelled in that tablet. This establishes that the same amount is being given with every tablet.

4) Assay Test: The test indicates the quantity of active drug in the tablet for its percent. In this case, a portion of at least 20 tablets is finely powdered. From this powder, a portion is extracted using pH 6.8 buffer, filtered, and then the obtained solution measured at 271 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer to read the absorbance while determining the drug concentration.

5) Thickness: The vernier callipers used. The thickness of each tablet is measured so that the size can be uniform. Each tablet placed between the two arms of the calliper measures its thickness, and all the tablets measure the same measurement.

6) Weight variation ^[2]: Take 20 tablets as random samples from a batch. Calculate the individual weight and average weight of tablets.

Specifications for Deviation: Average weight of the tablet is:

- Below 80 mg, single tablets are allowed to deviate $\pm 10\%$ of the average weight.
- Between 80 mg and 250 mg, tablets are allowed to deviate by $\pm 7.5\%$
- Above 250 mg, tablets are allowed to deviate by $\pm 5\%$

This test ensures that all tablets possess uniform weight, a critical parameter of dosing and hence of final product quality.

7) In vitro Dissolution study ^[17]: In an in vitro dissolution study, the rate and extent by which a drug is discharged out of its dosage form.

Dissolution apparatus: USP Type 1- Basket type And USP Type 2- Paddle type

Dissolution apparatus: Apparatus rotation speed: It follows the USP guidelines and employed rotation speed 100 RPM.

Dissolution medium: Phosphate buffer (pH 7.2); it is a body condition simulant. Each station holds 900 ml of this buffer solution. Aliquots of 5 ml were withdrawn at different time intervals to estimate the drug release by using a UV-visible spectrophotometer at a 271 nm wavelength.

8) Kinetics of Drug Release: ^[18] To understand the release of the drug from the tablets, kinetic models applied for the analysis of data obtained from the dissolution study. These models can best describe the release pattern and mechanism of the drug.

- Zero-Order Kinetics: This delivery is dependent on how long the process takes and does not depend upon the drug remaining in concentration. The release rate is independent of the drug concentration.

$$Q = Q + k_0 t$$

- Hixson-Crowell's Equation: In this model, change in surface area and shape of the dosage form as the drug dissolves is considered. This is actually used when tablets shrink with the release of the drug.

$$1/w_0^2 - w^1/t^3 = kt$$

- Higuchi Square Root of Time Equation: This square root of time equation models a drug release through diffusion, which is proportional to the square root of time, thus it is suitable for those formulations in which the release of drug is diffusion-controlled through a matrix.

$$Q = kt^{1/2}$$

- Korsmeyer-Peppas Equation: The model identifies the release mechanism, e.g., diffusion or erosion. It is more applicable for determining if the drug release follows a Fickian diffusion pattern.

$$M_t / m_\infty = k_t^n$$

9) Stability study ^[19]: These study done on the optimized tablet formulation as per ICH (International Conference on Harmonization) guidelines in this study, The tablets needs to place at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity for six months and sampling intervals at 1,3 and 6 months. Samples of tablets were drawn at the end of every month. These were analyzed for the following parameters:

- **Physical Characteristics:** Visual observation on whether color is changed or texture, hardness, and friability are affected.
- **Drug Release Profile:** The in-vitro dissolution rate of the tablets was evaluated in order to observe whether there was a change in the drug release profile in the course of the study.

Cytotoxicity study: A cytotoxicity study is an evaluation of the toxic effects of drug or substance on living cells, which is crucial for determining safety and biological compatibility in fields like pharmacology and toxicology. Some of the key objectives are cell viability, dose-response relationships, and safety margins. Common methods include the MTT assay, LDH release assay, and flow cytometry, which measure aspects like mitochondrial activity, membrane integrity, and cell death mechanisms. Applications include drug development, chemical safety, medical device testing, and cancer research. Key metrics of interest include IC50 values, morphological changes, and exposure time-dependence. In vitro cytotoxicity testing is an important evaluation of pharmaceuticals and environmental studies in assessing the effects of potentially harmful compounds. It is very significant in pharmaceuticals and the environmental industry to detect harmful substances, which further aids the development of medical treatments. Sensitive and efficient traditional techniques relied on fluorescent or colorimetric stains in detecting cell death or particular metabolites.^[20]

CONCLUSION:

Controlled-Release lamivudine tablets mark an important landmark in the therapy of chronic viral diseases such as HIV and Hepatitis B. Lamivudine is a nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor used for the inhibition of viral replication; its short half-life makes it require frequent dosing, which limits therapeutic compliance. These systems prevent frequent dosing and drug accumulation, thereby reducing the risk of toxicity. This review focus on the profile of diseases caused by HIV and Hepatitis B and calls for improvement in treatment with quality of life improvement in patients. The management of co-infection due to HIV and Hepatitis B is a challenge, and controlled release lamivudine tablets could be interestingly used in enhancing adherence in addition to efficacy among patients who undertake such co-infection. In conclusion, controlled-release lamivudine tablets represent a new and effective means for the chronic management of HIV and Hepatitis B infections, overcoming important challenges in dosing frequency, drug stability, adherence by the patient and quality of life of patients.

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